

Agency

People who have **lived experience** of a particular context can describe it more effectively than those who do not. If researchers and product designers “**talked to enough people**”, they’d have worked out what they actually want to do”. Participants want meaningful **flexibility** when contributing to usability studies – not to have options dictated to them. A lack of flexibility robs them of their **agency** and impacts their energy for engaging in usability tasks. Whereas having **options** which are “**tailored**” means participants feel less pressured and more “**involved**” in the usability test.

Participant perspective

Usability studies should be **participant-centred**. This helps to create **space** for participants to express their viewpoint and communicate their needs. Participant-centred studies lead to **comfortable experiences** with “warm and open conversation”. Conversely, participants addressed a potentially unhealthy **power dynamic** that can lead to them feeling “anxious”, patronised or pushed. Participants do not want to feel “**judged**” if they cannot explain their choices in a usability test or “**embarrassed**” if they get something “wrong” whilst being observed.

Information transparency

Transparent information throughout the process is highly valued by participants. It helps them to **feel at ease** when **communicating their needs**. Receiving information and details about predefined usability tasks **in advance** lets participants “process them in their own time”. “**Checklists**” and “**step by step walkthroughs**” help participants to know what to expect in a usability study. Using “**plain**” language means participants are on a “**level playing field**”.

The participant usability journey

Initial findings for roundtable discussion

Trust

Trust impacts a participant’s willingness to engage with a usability study. **Establishing and maintaining** trust is an ongoing process. The **accuracy of information** and the **consent** process both help to support a sense of trust. Some **institutions** and **research teams** are perceived as more **trustworthy, credible** and **ethical** than others.

Discuss access needs

Some access needs are **invisible**. Also, usability studies should embrace **neurodivergence** and **cognitive diversity**.

Many participants expressed that they use **copng mechanisms** because they’re used to “**moulding and fitting in**”. Some commented that a **negative past experience** can impact their confidence to express needs. More positively, an effective **dialogue** about needs can lead to more **diverse recruitment**. Participants don’t want to feel like “someone who isn’t capable” even when being unable to use a product is “useful” to the usability study.

Time

Participants discuss the importance of having **breaks**. Some express that the time spent doing the usability tasks does not actually represent the full **time commitment**. Participants do not want their time to be **wasted** nor for it to be **undervalued**. Participants want time to be linked to **choice**. A mishandling of time can be associated with **negative feelings** of control, limited options and “being put on the spot”.

Sense of value

Participants discuss the **value** they can bring to usability studies because of their **lived experiences**. They want to know their contributions are “**useful**” in terms of making products and services usable, rather than just accessible. **Compensation** is an important way of **recognising** the value of participants’ contributions. They do not want to be “**mean and cheeky**” but want to feel “able to **invest their time**”.